

EXPLORING PSYCHOSOCIAL EXPERIENCES OF ONLINE FLINGS AMONG FEMALE YOUNG ADULT

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ABSTRACT

Online flings refer to short-term causal relationship or sexual encounter with no expectations of commitment or emotional attachment that primarily occur through digital platforms. The rise of online dating apps and social media has significantly impacted how individuals, including young adults, engage in romantic and sexual relationships. The present study explored the psychosocial experiences of online flings among female young adults. Purposive sampling strategy was used to collect the sample of (N=8) females who involve in doing online flings or making online relationships. The sample was recruited from institutions. Demographic sheet and interview protocol was used to gather the data. In order to analyze the data, interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) was used. The findings revealed that there was one main theme i.e., manifestation of psycho-social experiences. Two superordinate themes emerged i.e., psychological experiences and social experiences. Eight subordinate themes emerged by analyzing the data. Psychological experiences comprised four subordinate themes i.e., intrinsic motivation, emotional turmoil, impact on self-esteem and fear of abandonment. Social experiences comprised of four subordinate themes i.e., phubbing, social influence, companionship seeking and inadequate family support. The total number of codes extracted from the data was 59. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that mental health professionals and educational institutions develop targeted interventions to address the psychological and social challenges faced by young adult females engaging in online flings. These interventions could include workshops on digital relationship dynamics and support groups to foster healthier online interactions and emotional well-being.

Keywords: Online flings, Psychosocial experience, Young Adult.

INTRODUCTION

The rise of online dating apps and social media has significantly impacted how individuals, including young adults, engage in romantic and sexual relationships. Navigating the world of dating can be a complicated and confusing process. This shift has brought about changes in the dynamics, expectations, and experiences of these

relationships. Typically, flings are driven by physical attraction, convenience, and a desire for pleasure without any deeper connection. Fling partners often engage in one-time hook ups or occasional dates without any intention of a long-term relationship. Fling partners may meet through social networks or dating apps and have

minimal communication or engagement outside of casual hook ups which usually last a few weeks to a few months, depending on the participants' preferences and schedules (Smith, 2023).

1.1.1 Types of Online Fling

Short and often casual romantic or sexual encounters that primarily occur on internet-enabled platforms are known as "online flings." These online flings differ from conventional dating and courtship due to their fleeting nature and reliance on digital communication methods. Conventional dating and courtship typically involve physical interactions and ongoing personal connections. Participants in online flings may engage in flirtatious exchanges, private conversations, or virtual meetings with individuals they encounter online, often without the expectation of a lasting relationship or deep emotional involvement (Khattar et al., 2023).

1.1.1.2 Casual Hookups. Casual hook ups represent one of the most common types of online flings, characterized by brief and non-committal sexual encounters between individuals who meet through digital platforms. Participants may seek physical gratification or companionship without the expectation of developing a romantic relationship or emotional attachment. Casual hook ups often emphasize spontaneity and excitement, with participants engaging in casual sex or intimate activities with minimal prior communication or personal disclosure (Gong & Huang, 2023).

1.1.1.3 Virtual Flirting. Virtual flirting involves the exchange of flirtatious messages, photos, or videos through online messaging apps, social media platforms, or dating websites. Participants in virtual flirting may engage in playful banter, compliments, or suggestive conversations as a means of expressing romantic or sexual interest in each other. Virtual flirting can range from harmless interactions aimed at boosting self-esteem or social validation to more explicit exchanges intended to initiate physical intimacy or romantic involvement (Johnson et al., 2016).

1.1.1.4 Cybersex and Sexting. Cybersex and sexting entail the exchange of sexual messages, images, or videos between individuals over digital communication channels. Participants may engage in erotic role-playing, mutual masturbation, or explicit conversations about sexual fantasies and desires. Cybersex and sexting can serve as a form of sexual expression or exploration, allowing individuals to satisfy their sexual urges and fantasies in a virtual context. However, these activities also carry risks related to privacy, consent, and online safety (Toma, 2022).

1.1.1.5 Emotional Affairs. Emotional affairs involve the development of intense emotional connections or romantic attachments with individuals met online, often in the absence of physical intimacy. Participants in emotional affairs may share intimate details about their lives, confide in each other, and seek emotional support or validation from their online partners. Emotional affairs can blur the boundaries between platonic friendship and romantic involvement, leading to conflicts and dilemmas in offline relationships (Oakenfull, 2024).

1.1.1.6 Long-distance Relationships. Long-distance relationships are a specific type of online fling characterized by the geographical separation of partners who maintain their relationship primarily through digital communication. LDRS often involve regular video calls, text messages, and virtual dates as a means of sustaining emotional intimacy and connection across distance. While partners may require greater effort and communication skills to maintain, they can also provide opportunities for personal growth and deepening emotional bonds between partners (Mengzhen et al., 2023).

1.1.1.7 Online Dating Sites. Humans possess an inherent and fundamental desire for purpose and belonging. Young adults, particularly those aged 18 to 25, exhibit a strong inclination towards establishing connections and frequently utilize their interpersonal relationships to define their identities (Allen, 2008). A significant avenue through which individuals fulfil this need is by forming meaningful romantic relationships. In

contemporary society, an increasing number of young individuals are resorting to online dating platforms and mobile applications in their quest for love and emotional connection. Since the inception of the first online dating site in 1995 and the emergence of modern social networking dating platforms in 2007, the online dating sector has evolved into a multi-billion-dollar industry with a vast user base. Currently, it is estimated that nearly 2 billion people globally engage with some form of online dating (Finkel et al., 2012).

1.1.1.8 Tinder and Mobile Dating. Tinder is a mobile application designed for social networking that operates based on the user's geographical location. It enables users to express their interest in others by liking or disliking profiles, and facilitates communication between users who mutually express interest. The platform serves as a dating site, attracting individuals with various intentions (Sumter et al., 2017). As reported by Google Play, by 2019, Tinder had facilitated 30 billion matches, establishing itself as the leading app for meeting and dating new individuals globally. The app generates over 26 million matches daily and holds a 4.00 rating on Google Play. Launched in September 2012, it quickly gained traction, amassing 10 million daily active users (Shapiro et al., 2017).

1.2 Dating and Anxiety

Individuals experiencing high levels of social anxiety often turn to the internet as a means to forge new connections, engage with others, and alleviate feelings of loneliness (Ebeling-Witte et al., 2007). Those who struggle with dating anxiety are more inclined to pursue online dating compared to those with heightened levels of dating anxiety (Vaulkenburg & Peter, 2007). Research by Sumter et al. (2017) and Timmermanns & De Caluwe (2017) indicates that the popular dating application Tinder is closely linked to various motivating factors such as affection, open relationships, self-esteem, and enjoyment, despite findings suggesting that the primary motivation for users is the pursuit of love (Sumter et al., 2017; Timmermanns & De Caluwe, 2017). Additional motivations for utilizing online dating platforms include seeking companionship, alleviating

boredom, enjoyment, and social interaction (Couch & Liamputtong, 2008; Carpenter & McEwan, 2016). Furthermore, studies have revealed that men tend to be more active on dating applications than women (Vaulkenburg & Peter, 2007). This difference can be attributed to the fact that women's engagement with dating apps is often influenced by social considerations, while men are more focused on casual encounters (Clemens et al., 2015; Sumter et al., 2017). Donn and Sherman found that 7.7% of young adults and 19.7% of undergraduate students have utilized the internet to seek potential romantic partners.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

1.3.1 Social Penetration Theory

Social Penetration Theory sheds light on how relationships develop through communication. It explores the process of building connections between two people. Imagine relationships as layers, with superficial interactions on the outside and deeper intimacy within.

SPT goes beyond physical closeness to consider intellectual and emotional closeness too. Sharing details about daily activities plays a crucial role in this process (West et al., 2010). Social Penetration Theory isn't just for face-to-face interactions it applies to online dating as well. This theory suggests that online communication, through dating apps or social media, can be a breeding ground for connections. Sharing personal information online, even if it happens quickly compared to in-person interactions, lays the foundation for deciding to meet up later. Interestingly, couples in committed relationships who use social media together might find themselves asking deeper questions and sharing more personal details online. This increased self-disclosure online strengthens their bond according to Social Penetration Theory, which emphasizes the importance of sharing personal information to build intimacy.

1.4 Casual Sexual Relationships and Emotional Experiences

Scholars who adopt a feminist lens contend that women are more prone to suffer negative emotional repercussions from casual sexual

relationships and experiences (CSREs) compared to men, largely due to the gendered dynamics surrounding sexual encounters (Allison & Risman, 2013; Kelly, 2012). These relationships unfold within a sexual double standard, where men receive social accolades for engaging in sexual activity, while women face social penalties (England & Bearak, 2014; Farvid & Braun, 2018). Script theory further supports this viewpoint by highlighting that sexual scripts are influenced by gender, often discouraging women from expressing their sexual or relational desires to their CSRE partners (Backstrom et al., 2012; Karlsen & Træen, 2013; Littleton et al., 2009). Nevertheless, not all theorists agree that women endure more adverse emotional effects from CSREs than men. Some feminist academics argue that these experiences can be empowering for women, as they represent a reclamation of their sexuality and a challenge to the restrictive norms governing women's sexual behavior (Kalish & Kimmel, 2011).

1.5 Worldwide Prevalence

Online flings, also known as virtual or internet-based relationships, have become increasingly prevalent among young adults, particularly with the widespread use of social media, dating apps, and online communication platforms. Studies have shown that a significant portion of young adult females engage in online flings, either as a form of casual dating, experimentation, or seeking emotional connection. The prevalence of online flings among young adult females varies depending on cultural, societal, and individual factors. The estimation of the global frequency of online flings reveals a dynamic and complicated environment influenced by the interaction of human actions, technical improvements, and cultural norms. Because online interactions are secretive, it is difficult to determine exact numbers; nonetheless, empirical data indicates that online flings are becoming more and more common in a wide range of geographic locations and demographic categories (Castro & Barrada, 2020). Research has shown that young adults in Western societies such as the United States and Europe engage in internet flings with noteworthy regularity. According to surveys done among

young professionals and college students, a significant percentage of them typically between 30% and 50% or more—have engaged in flirty or intimate encounters made possible by internet platforms. Moreover, a significant portion of people actively pursue romantic or sexual relationships in virtual environments, which has led to the standardization of online flirtation practices. This is due in part to the widespread use of dating apps and online communication platforms (Bleize et al., 2023).

Literature Review

Chakravarty et al. (2023) conducted a brief literature review to examine the effects of online dating on adolescents, with a focus on the Indian context. A search of PubMed and Google Scholar was performed in September 2022, without date restrictions, using keywords related to online dating, social media, mental health, and adolescents. English-language original studies and review articles were included. A descriptive approach was used to summarize the findings. The impact of online dating on adolescents was analysed in terms of (1) associated issues, (2) the global context, and (3) the Indian context. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, online dating among adolescents has increased, leading to concerns about sexually transmitted infections, dating violence, and mental health problems. These issues are often linked to unsupervised technology use, peer pressure, and societal expectations. Notably, there is a paucity of Indian data on this topic, emphasizing the need for further research into the influence of online dating on Indian adolescents.

A research study conducted by Thomas et al. (2023) examined the phenomenon of excessive swiping, defined as the mental fixation of youth on browsing profiles and compulsive swiping behavior. The study explored two moderating factors: swiping in assessment mode, which involves critically evaluating profiles, and locomotion mode, characterized by making intuitive decisions. To achieve this, a quota-sample of 464 dating app users aged 16 to 25 was surveyed. The moderated mediation analyses revealed a correlation between dating app usage and excessive swiping, which was further

associated with a) upward social comparison, b) anxiety about being single, and c) an overload of partner choices. In summary, frequent use of dating apps was linked to negative outcomes primarily when it involved excessive swiping. Neither assessment nor locomotion modes influenced these relationships, indicating that excessive swiping adversely affects the well-being of young dating app users, regardless of their swiping approach.

Another study by Strübel and Petrie, (2022) was conducted to examine Tinder use, gender, and related factors in a sample of 18-34-year-old men (n=187) and women (n=547). Factors included internalization, appearance comparison, body satisfaction, self-esteem, sociocultural pressures, depression, negative mood, body surveillance, body shame, body appreciation, and dietary intent. Regardless of gender, Tinder use correlated with increased distress across sociocultural pressures, internalized appearance ideals, body image concerns, and negative affect. However, Tinder use showed no connection to psychological well-being or eating pathology. These findings expand previous research, highlighting the potentially harmful environment for Tinder users. Marston and colleagues (2023) undertook research titled "Shiver Me Tinders and Ring a Ding for a Fling Sex Tech Use during COVID-19: Findings from a UK Study." The study aimed to explore the ways in which older adults engaged with dating applications during the UK's lockdown period from December 2020 to May 2021. The results highlighted in this report are derived from qualitative data obtained through an online survey and eight individual online interviews with participants aged 40 to 54 years. The online survey was distributed to adults throughout the UK, while the interview participants were situated across various regions of England. Oflaz et al. (2022) carried out a study aimed at exploring the mediating effect of dating violence victimization (PDVV) on the relationship between sexist attitudes and the emotions of guilt and shame. The research involved 219 college women from Turkey, a society where individual self-worth is heavily influenced by personal evaluations and societal perceptions. The study revealed significant levels of PDVV within this

cultural context, and structural equation modelling indicated that PDVV served as a mediator between sexism and the feelings of guilt and shame. The authors discuss the implications of these findings for future research and suggest ways to challenge sexist attitudes in order to mitigate the negative emotional consequences faced by women who experience psychological dating violence.

Bonilla-Zorita et al. (2020) conducted a systematic review of research on problematic online dating use. Despite the increasing popularity of online dating platforms and apps, limited research exists on this topic, with previous studies focusing primarily on personality correlates and scams. The review analysed 43 studies from PsycINFO and Web of Science databases, examining factors such as user motivations, personality traits, negative outcomes, sexual and impulsive behaviours, substance use, behavioural addictions, and overall problematic use. Findings indicate that personality traits like neuroticism, sociability, sensation-seeking, and sexual permissiveness correlate with increased online dating use. Motivations such as casual sex and self-esteem enhancement predict problematic use. The review aligns with existing research highlighting risks like deception and objectification associated with online dating platforms. Methodological limitations and suggestions for future research are also discussed.

2.1 Indigenous Studies

Alam et al. (2011) investigated young adults' attitudes towards online social networks and dating sites, as well as gender differences in online dating behaviour. The study found that most young adults have Facebook accounts, but only a small percentage actively use online dating platforms. A key finding revealed distinct gender-based online dating goals: women primarily sought long-term partners, while men tended to focus on casual relationships. A study by Sohail et al., (2019) aimed to explore how the Uses and Gratifications theory elucidates online dating behavior, focusing on Tinder usage within Pakistan. A survey targeting Tinder users aged 18-40 in Islamabad, Lahore, and Karachi, where usage is reportedly high, was conducted. The majority of respondents identified as Muslim.

Findings indicated that Tinder primarily serves as a tool for fulfilling users' needs, including relationship formation, sexual gratification, friendship development, and leisure activities. Moreover, the app addresses psychological needs like companionship and social needs such as expanding one's social circle.

Aksar et al. (2022) explored the presentation and performance of Pakistani women's selfhood and identity within both physical and digital spaces, influenced by the country's male-dominated cultural norms. Drawing on Goffman's concepts of self-presentation and performance, the study examined the online identities of ten Pakistani women from diverse backgrounds through qualitative interviews. Participants described conflicts between their offline and online identities, constrained by prevailing cultural values. The study highlighted the online manifestation of offline cultural norms, such as the veil, as a patriarchal mechanism controlling women's online behaviour, analogous to the male-protected family and home as physical sanctuaries. The concepts of "digital veil" and "digital sanctuary" were introduced to characterize Pakistani women's online experiences. Findings revealed a discrepancy between offline and online self-presentation among Pakistani women social media users, leading to identity crises shaped by cultural regulations. The study underscores the need for further research on the interplay between social and cyber cultures in offline and online identity formation, with a focus on psychosocial implications. Khan, (2020) conducted a study to determine the extent to which online dating applications that are prohibited influence Islamic culture and Pakistani youth. The study employed a quantitative research technique and aimed to investigate both positive and negative outcomes. 150 people were sent an online survey using Google Forms; 73 of them took part. The Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA) banned many applications, including SayHi, Tagged, Skout, Grindr, and Tinder, because of their alleged lewd content. These apps were the subject of the study. The results showed that these dating applications mostly have a detrimental impact on Pakistani youth and Islamic cultural norms.

2.2 Rationale

Online flings among young adult females holds significant clinical and academic value in the context of growing media exposure. With online platforms becoming a primary space for social interaction and relationship exploration, understanding these flings is crucial. Clinically, it can inform interventions to address potential negative consequences like loneliness or unrealistic expectations. Academically, it can contribute to a growing body of research on the impact of online environments on intimacy and relationships. By exploring motivations, emotions, and outcomes specific to young women, this study sheds light on a demographic with potentially unique experiences in the realm of online flings. This knowledge can inform future research and guide the development of support systems for young women navigating the complexities of online connections in today's media-saturated world.

2.3 Objectives of the Study

- To explore psychosocial experiences of online flings among young adult females
- To investigate the motivations and reasons behind female young adults engaging in online flings.

2.4 Research Question

- What are the psychological experiences of online flings among young adult females
- What are the social experiences of online flings among young adult females
- What are the primary psychological and social factors that motivate young adult females to engage in online flings?
- What are the potential positive and negative psychological and social consequences of online flings for young adult females?

Method

This section outlines the research methodology used in this study to explore the psychosocial experiences of young adult females engaged in online flings. The section details the rationale behind using interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA), participant recruitment strategies,

data collection procedures through semi-structured interviews, and the analytical framework of IPA for interpreting participant narratives. By systematically detailing the research process, this section aimed to ensure the reliability and validity of the study, offering a clear framework for understanding the methods used to gather and analyse data. The chosen methodology aligns with the study's objectives and research questions and provides a foundation for investigating the complex dynamics and psychological impacts of online flings among young women.

3.1 Research Design

This study used a qualitative phenomenological research design to investigate the psychosocial experiences of young adult females engaged in online flings. This approach prioritizes understanding participants' subjective realities, perceptions, social experiences and emotions surrounding online flings. Qualitative research is particularly well-suited for this purpose, as it allows for an in-depth exploration of the complex dynamic's characteristic in digital romantic interactions, which may be missed by quantitative methods. By adopting a phenomenological lens, the study focuses on capturing the lived experiences of young women as they navigate and perceive the phenomenon of online flings.

3.2. Sampling

3.2.1 Sampling Strategy

The study used a snowball sampling strategy to recruit participants. Asked initial participants to refer others who meet the criteria. This was effective in reaching a community of individuals with similar experiences relevant to the research question their "lived experiences" of online flings.

3.2.2 Sample Size

A volunteer sample of 12 participants with age range 18 to 30 years old were chosen and interviewed until reaching saturation. Saturation refers to the point at which no new significant information emerges from further interviews, indicating sufficient data has been collected for analysis.

3.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria of the Study

3.3.1 Inclusion Criteria

Participants were selected based on the following characteristics.

- Study participants must be female and aged between 18 and 30 years.
- Females must have engaged in at least one online fling within the past year.
- Participants must understand both English and Urdu language to ensure clear communication during interviews.
- Female must be willing to share their personal experiences related to online flings.
- Participants must provide informed consent to participate in the study.
- Participants should demonstrate a basic level of **digital literacy**.
- Participants should either be **single or casually dating**, without involvement in a long-term committed relationship.
- Participants should have an **active online presence**, using platforms such as social media, dating apps, or other digital communication channels.

3.3.2 Exclusion Criteria

Participants were excluded for the following characteristics.

- Participants were currently involved in a serious offline romantic relationship that may conflict with the study's focus on online flings.
- Participants with any diagnosed mental disability were excluded.
- Male participants were excluded from the study.
- Participants whose age is less than 18 years were also excluded from the study.

3.4. Data Collection

Social media platforms, dating apps, and online communities were utilized where young adults are likely to be present. Interested individuals were asked to complete a brief survey to determine if they meet the specified criteria (age, gender, online fling experience). Once potential participants are identified, conducted in-depth interviews to gather detailed information about their psychosocial experiences in online flings. Open

ended questions were used to encourage participants to share their stories and perspective

3.5 Procedure

University department helped us obtain the official university approval we needed to begin our research, and they graciously provided us with the necessary permission letter. Recruitment targeted young adult females with experiences in online flings. Both the informed consent form and participant information sheet clearly explained that interviews would be audio recorded. Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants were free to withdraw at any point. Confidentiality and anonymity were guaranteed. Aligned with Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), this study utilized in-depth, semi-structured interviews to capture the lived experiences of young adult females with online flings. This approach allowed for exploration of the research questions while also providing participants the freedom to delve into unexpected aspects of their experiences that might hold significance. Interviews, conducted took place online either on phone call or zoom ensuring privacy. Rapport was established with interviewees. Interviews were conducted in the participants' native language (Urdu) and then translated into English for analysis.

Anonymity was maintained throughout the transcription process. The average interview duration was 35 minutes. For any ambiguity or lack of clarity during the interview, the researcher clarified directly with the participant. To ensure comprehensive data collection and facilitate subsequent analysis, all interviews were audio recorded with participants' informed consent. This approach allowed the researcher to prioritize active listening and rapport-building during the interview, knowing that a complete record of the conversation would be available for detailed review.

3.6 Interview Protocol

The study employed a semi-structured interview schedule designed to progressively delve deeper into participants' experiences. The protocol began with broad, general questions and gradually transitioned to more specific ones. This flexibility

ensured the interviewer could maintain an active listening role, adapting the flow of questions to naturally follow participants' unique concerns and narratives. The semi-structured format facilitated exploration of participants' ongoing psychological and social experiences surrounding online flings, aiming to capture their lived realities.

- Can you describe your overall experience with online flings?
- Have these experiences influenced yourself self-image in anyway?
- Have you encountered any emotional challenges related to online flings?
- Can you share any emotional benefits you've experienced from online flings?
- What impact do online flings have on your mental health?
- How has the experience of online flings influenced your perspective on intimacy and commitment in a relationship?
- How do your online flings affect your social relationships or interactions in your offline life?
- How online flings affect your serious relationship of your life?
- How engaging in online flings has affected your view about yourself socially?
- Have you experienced any negative social consequences related to your online flings?
- Have you noticed any changes in the dynamics of your existing social circle since engaging in online flings?
- Have you noticed any changes in the types of social activities you participate in since engaging in online flings?
- Can you describe a specific situation where an online fling impacted your social life?
- Do you feel your online flings have impacted your ability to form or maintain in-person relationships?

3.7 Data Analysis

The data collected from the structured interviews were analysed using IPA, a qualitative approach that systematically identifies, organizes, and interprets patterns or themes within the data. Transcripts were read and reread multiple times, aiming to internalize the participants' voices and

perspectives. Audio recordings (if available) were listened to alongside initial transcript readings. Semantic content and language use were analysed on a preliminary level, focusing on themes, rapport building, and identifying sections rich in detail. Wide margins were added to transcripts, and lines were numbered to facilitate theme identification. Semantic content and language use were further explored. Interesting passages, striking issues, and anything relevant to participants' lived experiences were noted in the margins. A focus on core comments with a clear phenomenological lens was maintained, staying close to participants' explicit meanings. Notes from Step II were reviewed to identify patterns and connections. The goal was to condense data while maintaining complexity in theme interrelationships.

Themes were identified and labelled. Connections between themes were sought to group them meaningfully and identify overarching "superordinate" themes. Commonalities between subthemes were identified to name the "superordinate" theme. (Smith & Osborn, 2003). Each case (participant data) was analysed individually, seeking new or unexpected themes. Ideas emerging from previous case analyses were temporarily set aside ("bracketed") to avoid bias when analysing new cases. Connections and divergences between themes across cases were explored. How a theme in one case illuminated another was considered. Based on cross-case comparisons, themes were potentially reconfigured, relabelled, and integrated into a master table summarizing subordinate/subthemes, themes, and superordinate themes across all cases.

3.8 Ethical Consideration of the Study

Ethics were followed during the study:

- Ensured voluntary participation and informed consent from all participants.
- Protected the confidentiality and anonymity of participants' data.
- Minimized the potential harm or distress to participants throughout the study.
- Maintained transparency and honesty in all aspects of the research process.

- The participants were asked for their consent before taking part in the study.
- The participants have the right to withdraw from the study at any point they felt the need to.
- It was made sure that information gathered from the participants is strictly used for educational purposes.

Result

It presents the findings of this research based on the psychological and social experiences of young adult females engaged in online flings. Data was collected using interviews and then it was analysed using interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA). Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) is a qualitative method that seeks to give in-depth assessments of personal lived experiences. It provides an account of lived experience in its own terms rather than one shaped by pre-existing theoretical beliefs, and it acknowledges that this is an interpretative endeavour because humans are sense-making beings (Smith & Osborn, 2015). It is idiographic as it provides an in-depth analysis of each cases and highlight the individual perspectives of study participants, in their unique contexts (Pietkiewicz & Smith, 2012). In IPA, the analytical process is described as a twofold hermeneutic or dual interpretation process. Participants create meaning for their reality, and the researcher decodes that meaning to make sense of it (Smith and Osborn, 2008).

The objective of my research was to explore psychological and social experiences of females involved in online flings. For exploring this phenomenon by considering the subjective experiences of individuals, I conducted interviews of eight females involved in online flings. In order to analyse the data, interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) was used. There was only one main theme i.e., manifestation of psycho social experiences. Two superordinate themes emerged i.e., psychological experiences and social experiences. Eight subordinate themes emerged by analysing the data. Psychological experiences comprised four subordinate themes i.e., intrinsic motivation, emotional turmoil, impact on self-esteem and fear of abandonment.

Social experiences comprised of four subordinate themes i.e., phubbing, social influence, companionship seeking and inadequate family

support. 59 codes were extracted by analysing the data.

4.1 Table of Themes

Main theme	Superordinate theme	Sub ordinate themes	Codes
Manifestation of psycho social experiences	Psychological Experiences	Intrinsic Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pleasure in interaction • Formation of emotional bond • Enjoyment of companionship • Approval and Recognition • Seeking and Receiving Attention • Experiencing excitement • Sense of desirability and validation • Sharing a strong bond and availability
		Emotional Turmoil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frustration • Sadness • Emotional distress • Interpersonal Envy • Mood instability • Crying at night • anxiety • Perceived Rejection

Impact on Self-esteem

- Mental disturbance
- Guilt
- Emotional damage
- Sleep disturbances
- Feeling disheartened
- Excessive worry
- Overthinking
- Distorted self-image
- Perceived Unattractiveness
- Lowered self esteem
- Enhanced confidence
- positive attention boost
- Unaffected self-perception

Fear of Abandonment

- Perceived Worthlessness
- Feeling Devalued
- Self-worth doubts for attention
- Perception of being unlovable
- Unworthiness of Affection

Social Experiences

Phubbing

- Rejection fear
- Interest loss fear
- Romantic Jealousy
- Fear of being ghosted
- Fear of being replaced
- Relationship uncertainty
- Insecurity
- social interactions avoidance
- interpersonal relations gap
- Group Outing Decline

- Reduced social interaction
 - Family interaction decline
 - Decreased Time in social engagement
- Social Influence
- Peer influence
 - Social media influence
 - Peer Recommendations
 - Peer pressure in digital dating
- Companionship Seeking
- Desire for companionship
 - Seeking satisfaction and fulfillment
 - Coping with loneliness
 - Unmet emotional needs in relationships
- Inadequate Support
- Family
- Lack of Familial Understanding
 - Family Love and Support Deficiency
 - Emotional Gap in Family Relationships
 - Lack of Family Bonding

4.2 Psychological Experiences

There are a lot of psychological factors and consequences of indulging in online relationships. People experience both sort of positive and negative emotions, it can affect one's self-esteem and self-worth. It influences the personality of a person indulged in these flings. Following are the subordinate themes that emerged by analysing the data.

4.2.1 Intrinsic Motivation

Three of the females mentioned this during their interviews. They defined intrinsic motivation in terms of happiness, strong connection,

attractiveness and they can easily share anything with someone. They reported that they experience happiness in the beginning of the relationship. They felt that their bond was strong, enjoyed having a partner in the beginning. They had a very positive experience at the starting phase of their relationship that act as a motivation for this relationship.

Intrinsic motivation is described as engaging in an activity for its intrinsic satisfaction rather than for some distinct outcome. When a person is intrinsically driven, he or she is moved to act for the enjoyment or challenge of the activity, rather than for external products, pressures, or incentives

(Oudeyer & Kaplan, 2007). Intrinsic motivation in context of online flings can be feelings of validation, desirability, happiness to be with a partner and strong connection. These things motivate a person to indulge in online flings. Participants reported it as.

“The beginning was great. I felt like we had a strong connection and that they were perfect for me. We would talk for hours on end. I felt like I had a strong bond with them. I felt like I could

share anything with them and that they would always be there for me. I really liked their personality and sense of humour”.

Another participant reported

“The positive emotion is that I'm happy right now. I'm attracted to him. It feels good to have a new person in my life. He's very nice. Everything seems positive right now”.

4.2.2 Emotional Turmoil

Five of the participants reported emotional turmoil in online flings. They described emotional turmoil in terms of negative emotions that they experienced like depression, insecurity loneliness, emotional damage and anxiety etc. Females reported that they experienced both positive and negative emotions in these online relationships. If they felt excited and happy, there was also fear of being replaced, insecurity, jealousy, sadness, depression and anxiety. Majority of the females reported positive emotions only in the beginning that later on converted into negative experience and emotions.

Emotional turmoil is a state of intense and frequently conflicting emotions that can cause severe suffering and disrupt normal functioning. Individuals in emotional upheaval may fail to regulate their emotions, resulting in mood swings, impatience, and relational difficulties (Hennah, 2023). Participants reported emotional turmoil as.

“I felt very lonely because of this. I also felt depressed. I would start crying a lot, especially at night when I knew no one was listening”.

“There's the insecurity that he might have blocked me or that he won't read my messages or that he has someone else in his life. These are just some of the things that happen”.

4.2.3 Impact on Self-Esteem

Five to six participants described how these online relationships affected their self-esteem. Frequent participants narrated that their self-esteem affected negatively because of these online flings. Online relationships affected the self-worth of females, they begin to question their worth and importance, considered them used and unimportant. Due to more emotional investment by females, majority of the females had negative experiences. If a person does not get the desired attention and validation, it definitely affects their self-image and self-esteem. One of the females reported that if you do not have expectations then it doesn't affect your self-esteem or self-image. For some females, it also boosts their confidence to some extent.

Self-esteem is a measure of a person's views and attitudes regarding his or her abilities and ideals (Zhao et al., 2021). Self-esteem refers to an individual overall positive evaluation to the self. He added, that high self-esteem consists of an

individual respecting himself and considering himself worthy (Khalek, 2017). Female participants in this research described self-esteem in terms of worthiness, validation and how much importance do they get. Participants reported about their self-esteem as.

"I started questioning my worth and wondering if I was good enough. I felt like he left me for another girl. So, I felt like I wasn't beautiful enough and that there was something wrong with me and that I couldn't make anyone happy".

"I felt a bit like, I'm a useless person for getting involved in this and not getting any importance."

"There are times when the superficial nature of these interactions makes me question my worth. I often find myself wondering if I'm being valued for who I truly am or just for my online persona".

"When they started ignoring me and then abruptly ended the relationship, it had a negative impact on my self-esteem".

4.2.4 Fear of Abandonment

Three of the females reported that they have insecurities and they have fear of rejection. Females defined this as constant fear of rejection that the other person might be with some other girl or have been cheating. They can block me at any time.

Fear of abandonment is unwarranted fear that people you love will leave you physically or

emotionally (Fritscher, 2024). This fear is very common in online relationships as we don't have any idea about the intentions of other person. Females reported this experience as

"There is Insecurity that he might be with someone else, feeling of fear that he blocked me, feel rejection".

“The uncertainty and occasional rejection lead to anxiety and low self-esteem, fear of being ghosted or replaced”.

4.3 Social Experiences

Online relationships influence real life relationships. Not only it makes a person ignore real life relationship but also influence the quality of interaction and the person start avoiding others and feel alone. When a person indulges in online relationship, they like to spend more time on screen. The similar experiences were narrated by most of the females.

4.3.1 Phubbing

Five to six female participants reported that they used to spend more time on their phones instead of being with their family and friends. They started to give less time to their real-life relationships. They used to spend more time using screen.

Chotpita and Douglas (2018) define phubbing as the act of snubbing someone in a social context by glancing at one's phone rather than paying attention to the other person (Garrido et al., 2021). Female participants also described it through their experience, they like to spend more time on phone, ignore real life relationships. They narrated their experiences as follows.

“When a person is involved in these kinds of things, they start to distance themselves from

others, and I was a bit like that, avoiding everyone. Everyone is sitting together, but I would get up and leave and go sit somewhere else where there was no one”.

“These online relationships have affected my social circle in a negative way. I spend less time with my friends and family because I am so focused on talking to the people I am connected with online. I also feel like I am more isolated and alone”.

“They sometimes distract me from my offline relationships, as I find myself more engaged in my phone than in real-life interactions with friends and family. I've had friends express concern about my constant use of social media and my preoccupation with online connections”. “Engaging in online flings has made me more aware of my social skills and the way I present myself. It has boosted my social confidence to some extent, but it has also made me more critical of how I come across to others. I often find myself overthinking my interactions and worrying about being judged by others”.

“I feel sad and lonely inside, and I just want to be alone and not have anyone call me”.

4.3.2. Companionship Seeking

Three females reported that they did not get the desire attention from their families or their bonds with their siblings and family was weak. The validation and attention that they can get from a partner is not possible to receive from their friends and family. Due to unstable relationship with closed family members, they indulge in online relationships.

Companionship is described as social involvement in shared activities, whether recreational or non-recreational, undertaken for the intrinsic purpose of fulfilment or enjoyment (Bromell & Cagney,

2014). Females defined companionship in terms of appreciation, attention and satisfaction. Participants reported as

“I think it was because I had a need for companionship”.

“I can say it this way, if you get a good gesture from the person in front of you, it is human nature that everyone wants to be appreciated and praised, so when I got that attention, I got involved in this. You don’t get that kind of attention from your family”.

“Got involved in this for sake of satisfaction, to fulfil needs”.

4.3.3 Social Influence

Some female participants reported that they indulged in online flings because of not getting enough attention from family members and siblings. Some of the participants reported that there is a tendency to indulge in this relationship because you see your friends doing it. Some involve in it on recommendation of friends.

Other individuals have an impact on an individual's beliefs, feelings, and actions, which is

known as social influence. It is an essential component of relationships both inside and between communities. Societal influence manifests itself in a variety of ways, including conformity, socialization, peer pressure, obedience, leadership, persuasion, minority influence, and societal transformation (Smith et al., 2011). Participants reported their experiences as.

“A friend of mine recommended it to me. She was doing it herself, so she told me it was a good thing and that it would increase my social interaction. So, I started it too”.

“I have a friend who told me about this and basically I started to live alone far away from

friends and family I was in a depressed environment. So, she told me that you can date online”.

4.3.4 Inadequate Family Support

It was narrated by few participants that they indulged in these relationships to overcome loneliness. Their bond with their families was not strong enough. They were not getting much support from their families.

Family support is defined as support provided to an individual through social ties with other people, groups, and the larger community (Yang et al., 2022). Participants reported their experiences as.

“I felt like I wasn't getting enough of that from my real-life relationships”.

“I have a friend who told me about this and basically I started to live alone far away from friends and family I was in a depressed environment. So she told me that you can date online”. “To overcome loneliness I started this relationship, but when he doesn't reply to me, it makes me feel even more alone. I think that I made a mistake and that I shouldn't have done this”. “His needs are not being met, he is not getting any satisfaction from his family member or anyone”.

4.5 Mind Map

Discussion

In today's digital media landscape, temporary romantic relationships have become increasingly common among young adults (Sanchez et al., 2017). This research seeks to explore the psychosocial challenges faced by young women during their online romantic engagements. Understanding these experiences is crucial, as internet-based relationships can significantly influence psychological well-being and social connections. Therefore, this analysis concentrated on uncovering the psychological dimensions of these interactions, aiming to investigate the essence of these relationships. The study provided insights into how young women navigate the intricacies of virtual intimacy, balancing the emotional fluctuations that often accompany online interactions with their inherent attraction. Interpretative phenomenological analysis was employed to identify key themes. The results revealed the psychological experiences of young adult females participating in online flings. These women exhibited intrinsic motivation for their involvement, with the primary motivator being the

enjoyment derived from interaction. The pleasure associated with virtual affairs stems from factors such as novelty, the safety of anonymity, and flexibility. Such engagements provide a respite from daily routines and can satisfy emotional needs without the complexities associated with physical intimacy.

The simplicity of the contact and quick supply through using online connections can also help the fun in having affair. This finding is consistent with previous study (Tandon et al., 2022). Another motivation factor is formation of emotional bond. This is especially because women may use online flings to seek for emotional consummation, love, acceptance and companionship. They can provide a feeling of closeness and entertainment, thus serving as a replacement for the lack of intimacy. Immediacy and lack of face-to-face contact reduces the barriers to the emotional disclosure. Also, given that the interactions are through online platforms, the frequency and consistency of the interactions enhance the development of the other elements of the emotional bond. This finding is consistent with previous study (Aliverdi et al., 2022). Another factor that motivated them to be in online flings is enjoyment of companionship.

These interactions give them the chance to satisfy some of their needs and explore different aspects of personality with their partners without strict bonds of partnership. The immediacy in interacting with others in virtual space makes it easy to cultivate and sustain these relationships, offering moments of affirmation and a means of avoiding the reality of life's challenges. This finding is consistent with previous study (Brady & Baker, 2022). An additional element to consider is the desire for approval and recognition. Women often engage in online affairs as a means to obtain emotional and psychological rewards from social networking platforms. These interactions can provide excitement and enhance self-esteem, particularly for those who may feel undervalued in their primary relationships or daily lives. The pursuit of this validation can become quite addictive, leading individuals to seek further interactions to experience more of these affirmations. This observation aligns with earlier research conducted by Habenicht and Schutte (2023).

Another factor is seeking and receiving attention. Interaction with an online partner lead to increased self-esteem and worth by the amount of attention paid to them. It is necessary to note that a desire to gain attention and recognition from someone, even if this is an online stranger, is one of the human needs. It is argued that this attention is of social approval and leads to increased self-esteem and confidence boost that might be taken over to other spheres of life. This finding is consistent with previous study (Goldberg et al., 2022). Another factor is sense of desirability and validation. Online flings can make young women feel good about themselves since they allow them to freely construct and perform their selves and sexual desires in ways they would not ordinarily experience in everyday offline interactions. Since the communication takes place online, they may speak and act freely, and this makes them feel liberated and satisfy. Another reason is to have someone around with whom one can discuss personal issues and bring out personal examples. The convenience of having an online partner to communicate with and address needs gives the user a feeling of company. It may reduce loneliness feelings and always have someone to listen and

respond to emotions, especially in a period of life known for instability, young adulthood. This finding is consistent with previous study (Tan et al., 2019). Another factor is sharing bond and availability. The means of sharing, as well as the emotional connection empowers them to attain a sense of intimacy and inclusion that contributes to their happiness and well-being. This finding of the research is consistent with previous study (Hamilton, 2016).

Females who were involved in online flings also experience emotional turmoil. One of the factors included in emotional turmoil is frustration. There are several reasons why women engaged in on-line romantic connections get frustrated: Some of the risks involved are; the partner may have unclear intentions, lack of face-to-face communication which may lead to misunderstanding, and probability of meeting fake individuals. When there is a delay in response or if the partner refuses to be transparent, reminiscence with the virtual partner will cause feelings of insecurity. Also, the fact that they cannot easily switch from an online relationship to an offline relationship may complicate matters even more. This finding is consistent with previous study (Chakravarty et al., 2023). Other factor is sadness. Emotional attachment that female participants in online romantic relationships develop leads them to feeling of loneliness and desire to meet the online partner, hence sadness. The feeling of insecurity and doubt regarding the partner's genuine interest and intentions, as well as the threat of being tricked, can strengthen these emotions. This finding is consistent with previous study (Bouffard et al., 2021). Other factor is emotional distress. Females are more likely to experience several types of negative emotions having online flings. Reason is the instability of fleeting, often even nonserious connections that nature of such encounters makes these designs intrinsically unpredictable. Such an environment can be charged with stress and insecurity, for the lack of determinate engagement or further anticipation may place women at a disadvantage and create doubts about their status within the online relationship. The feelings of insecurity can be enhanced by the threat of being dumped or replaced thereby resulting in

individuals being emotionally distressed and stressed 24/7. This finding is consistent with previous study (Jardmo et al., 2022).

Another factor is interpersonal envy. Women engaged in online romantic relationships are predisposed to interpersonal envy because of the filtered and frequently glamorous presentations of other partners on social media. Comparing with other people's ideal relationships can cause decreased self-esteem and sexual satisfaction of individuals. This envy is born out of competition and the craving to achieve what one perceives as the well-being and accomplishment of the other, wounding interpersonal relationships and one's self-worth. This finding is consistent with previous study (Pipal, 2021). Another factor is mood instability. The emotional roller coaster resulting from the ambiguity of the online romantic relationships may cause mood instability among the women involved. The lack of face-to-face conversations not only creates confusion and conflict, but also increases feelings of anxiety and insecurity in female partners. This finding is consistent with previous study (Lloyd et al., 2019). Another factor is crying at night. Women in online romantic relationships may cry at night because of loneliness, insecurity or uncertainties about their relationship status. These feelings can be magnified when the partner is not physically present. This finding is consistent with previous study (Portolan, 2022). One more factor is anxiety. Women in online romantic relationships may feel anxious because of the uncertainty of the future of the given relationship, the authenticity of feelings of their partners, and lack of touch and, therefore, the confirmation of their partners' feelings. This finding is consistent with previous study (Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2023).

Another factor is perceived rejection. This maybe because of misunderstanding of the tone or the timing of a message, lacking the non-verbal cues that help individuals to understand the intention behind the message and be vulnerable by investing emotions in a non-physical relationship. It might also be attributed to the possibility of delays in responses or lack of timely feedback, which might be perceived as disinterest or rejection. This finding is consistent with previous study (Hance et al., 2017). Another factor is mental disturbance.

This is due to the vagueness, especially in virtual contact causing the person to worry if the connection is secure or if the partner is genuine. Further, the contradiction between an online appearance and the real self leads to tensions and possible cognitive dissonance in these relationships, adding more stress and feelings of turbulence. All these combines to increase the likelihood of mental disturbance among the women in online romantic relationships.

This finding is consistent with previous study (Jardmo et al., 2022). Another factor is guilt. They experience guilt of failing to meet the societal and or personal standards of relationships. Also, the feature of anonymity and distance in their relations makes it possible for them to develop constant contradictions between their online and real-life engagements. This finding is consistent with previous study (Erevik et al., 2020). Another factor is sleeping disturbance. This maybe because of increased emotional activation and the stress of the unknown dynamics of Internet relationships. Excessive communication and interaction using social media can cause sleep interruptions. Constant anxiety about having or concealing online relationships can also lead to sleep disruptions. This finding is consistent with previous study (Sell et al., 2023). Another factor is excessive worry and overthinking. This may be because of the new and unsteady nature of their electronic connection. They might be afraid of being let down like in the case of betrayal, being lied to or not measuring up to the image posted on social media. Distance eliminates the possibility of face-to-face communication, including body language which, in turn, makes fears more persistent and constant overthinking. This finding is consistent with previous study (Ritter et al., 2022).

Furthermore, online flings had both positive and negative impact on young females' self-image and self-esteem. They have distorted self-image. To some extent the negative effects are rooted in the inherently unstable and non-serious nature of online interactions. When such affairs fizzle out or do not satisfy the emotional needs of people involved, it results in feelings of rejection and inefficiency which lead to poor self-image. This finding is consistent with previous study

(Firestone, 2022). They also experience perceived unattractiveness. The perception of being unattractive is likely to affect women in online romantic relationships because of social norms, pressure caused by social media influencers, and rejection from virtual partners. This finding is consistent with previous study (Adiyanto & Wulandari, 2017). Women in online flings also experience lower self-esteem. The absence of a solid, actual proof can effectively make women doubt their value, especially if they have an idea that the interaction is vulgar or manipulative in nature. It damages their self-esteem and contributes to a negative outlook where they can become submissive or objectified because they think it is what they deserve or the kind of people they are. This finding is consistent with previous study (Richter & Finn, 2021). Some women experience enhanced confidence. Online affairs can uplift their egos and boost their confidence since they would be receiving attention. The positive reinforcement that they read from their online associates can boost their self-esteem by making them feel sexy and worthy.

When these interactions are a positive or affirmative type, then it increases confidence level and leads for a better body image. This is especially the case if the attention garnered from the online world over makes up for the lack of praise in the real world. This finding is consistent with previous study (Adiyanto & Wulandari, 2017). They also experience positive attention boost. Some of the benefits women may get in a romantic relationship online are getting direct compliments, words from the partner that affirm that they find her attractive or sexually desirable, the excitement that stems from new romantic encounters, which in turn will boost the self-esteem and self-confidence levels. This finding is consistent with previous study (Portolan, 2022). They also experience perceived worthlessness. It is due to different reasons such as manipulation and neglect from the partners, unfulfilled expectations and broken promises, and effects of cyberbullying together with other negative comments made towards the ladies. This finding is consistent with previous study (Pirrone et al., 2024). They also experience feeling of devaluation. The reasons for feeling devalued include fluctuating communication in romantic

relationships through social media, commercialization of relationships, and unequal comparison between women and other potential partners that seem to be valued higher. This finding is consistent with previous study (Firestone, 2022). They also experience perception of being unlovable.

Females in online romantic connections likely feel unlovable because of the critique and rejection they receive, dealing with partners who are reluctant and insincere, and inhaling destructive societal expectations regarding looks and behaviours that devalue their worth. This is consistent with previous study (Richter & Finn, 2021). Women experience unworthiness of affection. They are often ironic or superficial; they are always compared to the staged, perfect self-presentation they see online, and their previous relationships with betrayal and rejection lead them to doubt that they deserve love and affection. This finding is consistent with previous study (Bhave, 2021). Women involved in online flings experience fear of abandonment. The experience rejection fear. This is because of the lack of personal contact and the possibility of doubt and insecurity. When there are no physical cues and body language, it is difficult to discern if one is interested in what is being said, creating tension. Also, due to previous painful experiences or social norms, the feeling of rejection or judgment is most likely to be amplified. This finding is consistent with previous study (Pipal, 2021). They may experience interest loss fear. This is because it is very easy to do so because the world is bound with so many other options on the internet. The relationship that is developed in this communication channel is not as strong as the personal relationship because there is no meeting personally. Also, the lack of face-to-face interaction and the absence of frequent and timely communication may result in questions about the partner's ongoing desire.

Finding is consistent with previous study (Halpern & Katz, 2017). They also experience romantic jealousy. This is because the interactions in such relationships are not clear, and people are unknown to their partners. The constant access to social media, and constant contact can result in feelings of insecurity, and fear of cheating.

Furthermore, the reduced direct contact weakens the chances of clearing misunderstandings and establishing relational trust. This finding is consistent with previous study (Peterson & Xu, 2023). They experience fear of being ghosted. Some distressing aspects of online romantic relationships include dangers that women face when they could be ghosted since disengagement from the relationship is possible by merely declining to respond in cyberspace environments. This makes it more challenging to anticipate the cause of unannounced absences because the other party cannot be seen and observed in person. This finding is consistent with previous study (Lloyd et al., 2019). They also experience fear of being replaced. This is because of the perceived flexibility with which partners claim to have access to new connections on the internet. Due to a seemingly endless supply of potential matches and casual nature of interactions, certain anxieties about being easily replaced by someone else that is considered even more desirable or compatible are more pronounced. This finding is consistent with previous study (Thomas et al., 2022). They experience relationship uncertainty and insecurity. This maybe because of unpredictable nature of these relationships. One can present themselves good or perfect online while in real life they may have toxic traits or maybe they are in online relationships just for time pass that leads to insecurity. This finding is consistent with previous study (Liu et al., 2019).

Women in online flings also had various social experiences like phubbing. They avoid social interactions and group outing decline. The online bonding makes many people lose interest in physical contact as they engage more in the online relationship. They are more comfortable in online communication which is feasible in every situation and any time. This finding is consistent with previous study (Benvenuti et al., 2020). They experience interpersonal relation gap and family interaction decline. This preoccupation with online partner can lead to a narrow circle of contacts, as time and emotional energy are spent not on face-to-face communication and family relationships. The opportunities to communicate online and the constant availability of friends seem more beneficial in comparison to real life

interaction, thus, people avoid going out with friends or neglect family gatherings. This finding is consistent with previous study (Danielsbacka et al., 2020). Women in online flings are also less interested in social engagement. This maybe because many of these interactions are established for superficial purposes and designed for casual, short-term use. Because the encounters are superficial and temporary, people become immersed in self-pleasure rather than building genuine relationships online. Also, the confidentiality associated with online communication diminishes the perceived relevance of conventional social networking. This finding is consistent with previous study (Quiroz & Mickelson, 2021).

Reasons for involvement in online flings were also explored. Among other reasons, the main reason of their involvement in online relationships is peer influence. Women feeling the need to uphold societal standards or peer pressure through online relationships shows how social acceptance and norms impact their behaviour in digital exchanges that males may not experience. Similarly, social conformity can take over a huge part of our roles when other people (friends or peers) around us are indulging in the online relationship. This finding is consistent with previous study (Paska & Laka, 2024). Women involved in online flings because of social media influence. Some women engage in online flings because social networks encourage recklessness by presenting thrill, affirmation, and casual relationships as acceptable and desirable. When people are exposed to images and ways of life that are so perfect on social media then ordinary interactions become normalized and flings become socially acceptable. Besides, the idea of being able to meet people without having to be close physically facilitates exploration and testing of the relationships.

This finding is consistent with previous study (Bouffard et al., 2021). Women may get involved in online flings because of peer recommendation. Whether this stems from the perceived norm or expectation of seeing others participate in such relationships, a result of wanting to "fit in" or feel at home within their social groups, women ultimately join because peers recommend them to do so by explaining different advantages of these

relationships. This finding aligns with previous study (Kumari et al., 2021). They may involve in online relationships because of peer pressure in digital dating.

The pressure of friends of course can be highly effective in contributing to this place of conformity and believe wise, the very advice to get into on-line relationships from a friend in and off itself is meant as an incentive reinforced by peer pressure. Again, it could also be out of the need to blend in with a wider community which has embraced romantic relationships as a social ladder or means of self-realization. In certain societies, being single is seen as odd and many people are now using digital platforms to find future spouses. It can therefore be difficult for some women not to look for and maintain connections through the internet despite the huge differences in their individual motivations or even preparedness such relationships. This finding is consistent with previous study (Sahak et al., 2014). Findings also revealed other reasons for involvement in online relationships. Females involved in online romantic relationships to fulfil their needs of companionship and seeking satisfaction and fulfilment. The online relationships offer continuous communication and emotional connection that mitigates solitude that may lead to feelings of loneliness or isolation. Working with an online partner means that women can have someone to talk to and laugh with at any time of day or night-no waiting for time zones, no breaking curfew-and even on days when they cannot bring themselves to leave the house.

Females were also involved in online relationships because of their inadequate family support. Because of lack of familial understanding, they get involved in online flings. They reported that their family didn't understand them, and they were not getting enough of attention and care from offline relationships. Females often resort to internet dating as a way of escaping from their negative family backgrounds and the feelings of being misunderstood and ignored. When emotional sustenance is missing, these homes are lonely and alienating. Because they understand them and give validation, online relationships provide an alternative for companionship and emotional connection; others do not. This finding is

consistent with previous study (Thomas et al., 2017). They get involved in online relationships because of emotional gap in family relationships. This is because they can reveal their true selves in this case since virtual connections have anonymity due to distance that creates empathy which may not be at home. These virtual connections help satisfy their unmet emotional needs because they contrast with personal experiences by providing care and attention towards what they say. In such cases, solace, understanding, a supportive presence is sought for to fill in the gaps created by inadequacies within family dynamics through internet connections made by women themselves. This finding is consistent with previous study (Sanchez et al., 2017).

5.1 Limitations

- Only females were included in this study.
- Data was collected from one city only.
- Data collection was difficult because in our society being involved in romantic relationships is not considered normal and people don't acknowledge it openly because of stigma associated with it.
- The study focuses on psychosocial experiences but **does not deeply explore the technological aspect** of online flings, such as how specific digital platforms or algorithms may shape or influence the nature of these interactions.
- The sensitive nature of the topic, particularly in a conservative society like Pakistan, may raise **ethical concerns** about confidentiality and data protection.
- The **sample size** may be relatively small, limiting the generalizability of the findings. Since the research focuses on qualitative data, it may not fully capture the wide range of experiences among young adult
- As a qualitative study, the interpretation of data is inherently subjective, and the **researcher's biases** or perspectives may influence how the participants' experiences are understood and categorized.

5.2 Suggestions

- In future studies, data should be collected from other cities also to increase the generalizability of results.
- Future research can be done by including males also to determine their psychosocial experiences and one can compare both genders' experiences.
- Future studies could expand the **age range** of participants to include both younger and older adults.
- To enhance the understanding of how **cultural values**, shape the psychosocial experiences of online flings, future research could include participants from **multiple cultural contexts**. A **cross-cultural comparative study** could shed light on how social norms, religion, and traditional values influence behaviors and psychological outcomes across different societies.
- Future studies could focus on developing **psychological interventions or support programs** to help individuals navigate the challenges of online flings.
- Future studies could examine how **online flings impact offline romantic relationships** and familial dynamics. By including individuals who are in both online and offline relationships, researchers could investigate how these two spheres interact, affect emotional well-being, and potentially create conflicts.
- Longitudinal studies can also be conducted as they are helpful while determining as to how females involving in online flings feels overtime. By following these women for a long period, researchers can see how their psychosocial experiences evolve over time.

5.3 Implications

- This study can direct mental health experts on the understanding of emotional difficulties and psychological effects related to online flings among many others thus enabling more specific and effective interventions for young females in such situations.
- The study's insights may inform educators, parents, and counsellors about the social dynamics that impact young women's lives. This will necessitate supportive communication that is open concerning online relationships

whose impact is likely to be caused in real-life scenarios.

- Additionally, the research highlights the need for digital literacy programs which can teach young adults about the risks and emotions associated with Internet flings in order to promote safer internet habits.
- A study like this could help policy makers come up with guidelines that would enable development of online dating platforms with features that safeguard users' emotional well-being while aiding mechanisms for those who are experiencing negative psychosocial consequences.
- This research lays groundwork for future inquiries into how these relationships affect adult female psychological health (psychosocial). Thus, it encourages deeper looks at where digital interactions meet mental health issues.
- The findings of this study could inform the development of online safety campaigns aimed at protecting young women from the psychological harm associated with online flings. Campaigns could focus on raising awareness about the risks of emotional manipulation, cat fishing, and cyberbullying, providing practical advice on how to navigate online romantic interactions safely.
- This research can help relationship counselors and therapists better understand the **unique emotional and psychological challenges** that stem from online flings.
- The study's findings may encourage **social media platforms** to revisit their policies around online interactions, especially those that may result in negative emotional outcomes.
- The research may lead to the inclusion of **digital intimacy and online relationships** in sexual education curricula.

5.4 Conclusion

This study offers an in-depth exploration of the psychological experiences of young adult females involved in online flings, highlighting the tension between personal desires and the rigid social norms of Pakistani society. By employing Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), the research identified three overarching themes and ten distinct themes, encapsulating a wide spectrum of experiences, from self-esteem issues

and social isolation to moments of emotional connection and fulfillment. The findings reveal a duality in these experiences—while online flings can offer temporary emotional gratification and escape from societal restrictions, they also bring significant psychological challenges, such as anxiety, guilt, and fear of social judgment. The cultural backdrop of Pakistan, with its emphasis on family honor and traditional values, exacerbates these challenges, leading to internal conflicts and emotional distress for many participants. In essence, this study not only sheds light on the psychological complexities associated with online flings but also underscores the broader societal pressures that shape these experiences. It calls for a deeper understanding of the evolving dynamics of modern relationships in conservative societies, emphasizing the need for psychological and social support systems that recognize and address these conflicting pressures.

References

- Abdel-Khalek, A. M. (2016). Introduction to the psychology of self-esteem. In *Self-Esteem: Perspectives, Influences and Improvement Strategies* (1st ed., pp. 1-23). Nova Science Publishers.
- Aksar, I. A., Firdaus, A., & Pasha, S. A. (2022). Virtual vs. Real Self: Gendered Presentation and Everyday Performance of Virtual Selfhood - A Case Study of Pakistan. *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, 47(1), 84-114. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01968599221089236>
- Backstrom, L., Armstrong, E. A., & Puentes, J. (2012). Women's negotiation of cunnilingus in college hook-ups and relationships. *Journal of Sex Research*, 49(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2011.585523>
- Benvenuti, M., Giovagnoli, S., Mazzoni, E., Cipresso, P., Pedroli, E., & Riva, G. (2020b). The relevance of online social relationships among the elderly: How using the web could enhance quality of life? *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Bhave, T. (2021). Romantic relationships, online dating, and mental health issues. In *IGI Global eBooks* (pp. 94-102). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8544-3.ch006>
- Chakravarty, R., Jagota, G., & Sahoo, S. (2023b). Impact of online dating on the adolescent population: a brief review of the literature with special reference to the Indian scenario. *Consortium Psychiatricum*, 4(3), 65-70. <https://doi.org/10.17816/cp222>
- Clark, R. D., & Hatfield, E. (1989). Gender differences in receptivity to sexual offers. *Journal of Psychology & Human Sexuality*, 2(1), 39-55. https://doi.org/10.1300/j056v02n01_04
- Clemens, C., Atkin, D., & Krishnan, A. (2015). The influence of biological and personality traits on gratifications obtained through online dating websites. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 49, 120-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.12.058>
- Danielsbacka, M., Tanskanen, A. O., & Billari, F. C. (2020). Meeting online and family-related outcomes: evidence from three German cohorts. *Journal of Family Studies*, 28(4), 1390-1415. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13229400.2020.1835694>
- Ellison, N. B., Heino, R., & Gibbs, J. L. (2006). Managing Impressions Online: Self-Presentation processes in the Online dating environment. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 11(2), 415-441. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2006.00020.x>
- England, P., & Bearak, J. (2014). The sexual double standard and gender differences in attitudes toward casual sex among U.S. university students. *Demographic Research*, 30, 1327-1338. <https://doi.org/10.4054/demres.2014.30.46>
- Fritscher, L. (2024, July 1). Understanding fear of abandonment. *Verywell Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/fear-of-abandonment-2671741>

- Gangestad, S. W., & Simpson, J. A. (2000). The evolution of human mating: Trade-offs and strategic pluralism. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 23(4), 573–587. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0140525x0000337x>
- Garrido, E. C., Issa, T., Esteban, P. G., & Delgado, S. C. (2021). A descriptive literature review of phubbing behaviors. *Heliyon*, 7(5), e07037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07037>
- Scandinavian Journal of Psychology, 64(2), 133–141. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjop.12878>
- Johnson, K., Vilceanu, O., & Pontes, M. C. (2016). Flirting Online and the Connection between the use of dating websites and dating Applications. *Association of Marketing Theory and Practice Proceedings*, 5.
- Sohail, S. A., Mahmood, Q., Khan, M. H., & Gull, Z. (2019). Tinder use among pakistani adults: a socio-psychological need perspective. *Deleted Journal*, 3(3), 316. <https://doi.org/10.25139/jsk.v3i3.1954>
- Stevens, S. B., & Morris, T. L. (2007). College dating and social anxiety: Using the internet as a means of connecting to others. *Cyberpsychology & Behavior/CyberPsychology and Behavior*, 10(5), 680–688. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2007.9970>
- Strübel, J., & Petrie, T. A. (2022). Tinder use, gender, and the psychosocial functioning of young adults. <https://thejsms.org/index.php/JSMS/article/view/1025>.
- Sumter, S. R., Vandenbosch, L., & Ligtenberg, L. (2017). Love me Tinder: Untangling emerging adults' motivations for using the dating application Tinder. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(1), 67–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2016.04.009>
- Kalish, R. A., & Kimmel, M. S. (2011). HOOKING UP. *Australian Feminist Studies*, 26(67), 137–151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08164649.2011.546333>
- LeFebvre, L. E. (2018). Swiping me off my feet. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 35(9), 1205–1229. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407517706419>
- Marston, H. R., Morgan, D., Earle, S., & Hadley, R. (2023). Shiver Me Tinders and Ring a Ding for a Fling—Sex Tech Use during COVID-19: Findings from a UK Study. *Healthcare*, 11(6), 897. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11060897>
- Novotney, A. (2019). The risks of social isolation. <https://www.apa.org>. <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2019/05/e-corner-isolation>
- Owen, J. J., Rhoades, G. K., Stanley, S. M., & Fincham, F. D. (2008). “Hooking up” among college students: Demographic and psychosocial correlates. *Archives of Sexual Behaviour*, 39(3), 653–663. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-008-9414-1>
- Peterson, M. L., & Xu, X. (2023). *Romantic Relationship Social Comparisons*. Routledge Resources Online - Psychology in the Real World. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780367198459-reprw241-1>
- Tan, K., Agnew, C. R., & Hadden, B. W. (2019). Seeking and ensuring interdependence: desiring commitment and the strategic initiation and maintenance of close relationships. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 46(1), 36–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167219841633>
- Vrangalova, Z. (2014). Does Casual Sex Harm College Students' Well-Being? A Longitudinal investigation of the role of Motivation. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 44(4), 945–959. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-013-0255-1>
- Wentland, J. J., & Reissing, E. D. (2011). Taking casual sex not too casually: Exploring definitions of casual sexual relationships. *The Canadian Journal of Human Sexuality*, 20, 75–91.

Zhao, Y., Zheng, Z., Pan, C., & Zhou, L. (2021). Self-Esteem and academic engagement among Adolescents: a Moderated mediation model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.6908>
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